

Inhibition of corrosion of mild steel with the exploitation of emeraldine base and some pretreatments

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Emeraldine base, a polyaniline, can passivate steel and thus protect steel from corrosion but does not adhere to the surface of the steel strongly. The pretreatments using aqueous solutions of alizarin sulfonic acid and ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) in combination with a little conventional polymer (Premium Plastic warp (PPW is plasticized PVC of Presto Products Company, Appleton WI) were found to be very successful in the inhibition of corrosion of mild steel.

Corrosion of steel is a global problem. Iron, the most frequently used and the most abundant metal of the earth is, however, a reactive metal and undergoes oxidation (rusting or corrosion) in contact with atmospheric oxygen and in the presence of moisture. Corrosion of iron deprives it of its mechanical strength and sheds scales of rust making metal bars, sheets, pipes, bridges and ship hulls thinner and weaker. Hence there is a dire need of preservation of the properties of metallic iron. Several methods have been used to inhibit the corrosion of iron. One of them is anodic passivation using electrical current or a conducting polymer which functions in a battery-type mode.

Iron has the inherent property of forming a passive layer on its surface in the presence of strong oxidizing agents. A very thin layer of iron oxides is formed on its surface which is impervious to oxygen and water and has high electrical resistance. Thus the iron beneath the passive layer is not oxidized or rusted.

Ord and Bartlett¹ showed that for the passivation of a given steel, a certain potential and an amount of current is required to maintain the passive layer intact i.e. to heal the damaged or punctured layer.

DeBerry² used the electrochemically deposited polymer polyaniline in the inhibition of corrosion of stainless steels 410 and 430 and showed conclusively that polyaniline coating can inhibit corrosion of stainless steel for a very long time. He monitored the open circuit voltage (V_{∞}) of steel in hydrochloric acid and found that it stayed above that of bare stainless steel for ~27 days. DeBerry apparently used an unknown degraded form of polyaniline.

We³ undertook a very systematic study on the passiva-

tion of stainless steels 410 and 430 and mild steel AISI 1 and C 4140 and found that SS 430 is passivated in the potential range of -0.2 to 0.85 V vs SCE. The current density needed to maintain and to heal the damaged passive layer is only $9 \mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$. This amount of current is very low. Such a potential and current can be provided by the conducting polymer, polyaniline. The two mild steels AISI 1 and C 4140 showed that the passivation of their surface can start at -0.4 V vs SCE. Polyaniline in the presence of 0.1 M hydrochloric acid can provide a potential of 0.36 V vs SCE but on shiny surfaces like those of platinum or steel it has the capacity to provide a potential of about 0.41 V vs SCE. Thus theoretically speaking polyaniline can create a passive layer on these two types of mild steel.

This paper deals with the use of the conducting polymer, emeraldine base, a form of polyaniline and some pretreatments.

In this communication we deal with the inhibition of corrosion of a mild steel, C 4140, using some pretreatments, coating with emeraldine base mixed with a conventional polymer and a corrosion inhibitor. Mild steel is used in making bridges, pipelines, automobiles, ships and in building construction and hence this method provides a practical means of corrosion prevention using polyaniline.

Results and discussion

The experiment using platinum coated emeraldine base in conjunction with steel coated with clear nail polish except for a small scratch clearly proves that emeraldine can inhibit the corrosion of steel C 4140 as the potential comes down to -0.5 in about 65 min whereas the potential of bare

Table 1. The steel plates were pretreated with alizarin or EDTA, and coated with emeraldine base along with other treatments. These were dipped in 0.10 M HCl solution and the V_{∞} measured versus SCE with time. The time taken by the steel strip to get down to a potential of 0.5 V was noted*

The steel samples were treated as given in this column, dipped in 0.10 M HCl and potential monitored versus SCE	Alizarin	EDTA
	0.005 M	Saturated
Pt coated with emeraldine base, connected with steel which was covered completely with clear nail polish except for a scratch, 10 mm × 1 mm made with a sharp razor blade.		
No pretreatment	65 min	
Steel C 4140 was coated with emeraldine base in TMU. No pretreatment	5 s	
Pretreatment and emeraldine base solution coating	8 min	3 min
Pretreatment + emeraldine + <i>N</i> -allylaniline	11 min	12 min
Pretreatment + emeraldine base coating + TiCl ₄ in cyclohexane	14 min	7 min
Steel dipped in a solution of TiCl ₄ in cyclohexane for 10 min, pretreated and then emeraldine base deposited on it.	2 min	Less than 2 min
Pretreatment + 1.0 ml emeraldine + 0.01 g PPW	10 min	230 min
Pretreatment + 1.0 ml emeraldine + 0.01 g PPW + 1 drop of <i>N</i> -allylaniline	37 min	44 min
Pretreatment + 1.0 ml emeraldine + 1 drop of <i>N</i> -allylaniline + (0.01 g PPW added just before coating)	49 min	100 min potential still
		-0.4808 V
*For details of first column, refer to text.		

steel in 0.1 M HCl comes to 0.56 V within about 3 min. The problem with coating emeraldine on mild steel is the lack of good adherence. Hence pretreatments are required.

A 1×10^{-6} M solution of titanium tetrachloride in cyclohexane was used in the hope that TiCl₄ will change to TiO₂, may form almost a nano layer and act as a catalyst to raise the potential of emeraldine base to 0.41 more quickly and help in the formation of the passive layer but it did not work.

The two pretreatments with alizarin and ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid are excellent. Addition of polyethylene to the solution of emeraldine base and using it as a stock solution does not seem to be a good idea because gelation takes place and clogs of the polymer are formed which do not let a uniform coating be made on the steel. A fresh solution of emeraldine base with polyethyl-

ene must be used for coating. Wroblewski *et al.* had used an antioxidant tinuvin 770 of Ciba-Geigy, to retard gelation. We did not try the antioxidant because it could be avoided by adding polyethylene to the emeraldine base solution in TMU at the time of coating the steel.

The corrosion inhibitor *N*-allylaniline provides little help. Pretreatment with a saturated solution of ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid for 60 s lets steel react with the acidic protons of EDTA and form a chelate using probably the two nitrogens and some of the carboxylic acid groups and the remaining carboxylic groups dope the emeraldine making it stick better on the steel and also converting the non conducting emeraldine base to conducting emeraldine salt. The emeraldine salt takes electrons from the steel and oxidizes the surface making a passive layer. The emeraldine goes to the lower oxidation state called leucoemeraldine which is again oxidized by the air and regenerates the emeraldine making it ready for healing the ruptured passive layer. Thus emeraldine should theoretically work for ever in the inhibition of corrosion of steels.

Alizarin sulfonic acid is also an excellent pretreatment. It was successful in the inhibition of corrosion of stainless steels⁴ also. The sulfonic acid group of alizarin reacts with iron surface producing ferrous ions which chelate with one of the two phenolic groups and the double bonded oxygen. The sulfonic acid group and the other phenolic OH dope the emeraldine base creating the emeraldine salt form.

The pretreatment with 0.05 M aqueous solution of alizarin for 60 s and the coating with emeraldine base containing 0.01g PPW per ml of saturated solution of emeraldine in TMU inhibits the corrosion of steel C 4140 for about 49 h. from the corrosive action of 0.10 M HCl.

The pretreatment with a saturated aqueous solution of EDTA for 60 s and the similar pretreatment with alizarin inhibits corrosion for 230 min. If the steel in automobiles is painted from outside and coated according to our method from inside it will go a long way in checking the rusting of the automobile bodies.

Experimental

Materials and method :

The steel C 4140 (from Metal Samples, Mumford, Alabama, composition : Al = 0.030%, Mn = 0.86%, S = 0.003%, C = 0.390%, Mo = 0.190%, Si = 0.300%, Cr = 1.07%, Ni = 0.080%, V = 0.001%, P = 0.015% Fe = balance) was purchased as strips, 5 cm × 2.5 cm × 0.2 cm. These were smoothed with 350, 400, 500 and 600 grit emery papers successively, washed with water and kimwipe, then with methanol and used immediately.

Coating with the polymer :

A steel strip was completely coated with clear nail polish, dried and a 10 mm × 1 mm scratch made with a sharp razor blade. It was electrically connected with a platinum foil 2.5 cm × 2.5 cm. Emeraldine base was dissolved in 1,1,2,2-tetramethyl urea. (TMU). NMP was not used because NMP on drying leaves a water soluble colorless residue and when the metal strip coated with emeraldine base solution in NMP is placed in the corrosive solution, NMP residue dissolves leaving holes which cause quick pitting corrosion. The dissolving power of TMU is higher for emeraldine base than that of NMP. The solution was centrifuged, the centrifugate was filtered through a filter paper to obtain a particle free saturated solution of emeraldine base. The emeraldine base was synthesized by the oxidative polymerization of aniline with ammonium peroxydisulfate in 1 M HCl. This clear solution (1 ml) of emeraldine base in TMU was placed on the platinum foil and dried. The platinum foil and the steel strip were connected to a multimeter, dipped in 0.10 M HCl solution and potential measured versus SCE with time. The potential decreased to -0.5 V in about 65 min. The bare steel dipped in 0.01 M HCl shows a potential of -0.56 V within about ~3 min. This clearly proves that emeraldine can inhibit corrosion of steel C 4140 for quite sometime from the corrosive action of 0.1 M HCl.

Coating with emeraldine base :

Coating of the strips of C 4140 only with emeraldine base solutions in TMU does not withstand the corrosive action of 0.1 M HCl for more than a few seconds i.e. the potential goes down to -0.5 V vs SCE. Hence pretreatments were tried.

Pretreatments and chemical deposition of emeraldine base on steel strip :

The two pretreatment solutions were the aqueous solutions of 0.05 M alizarin sulfonic acid and a saturated solution of ethylenediamine tetraacetic acid. The strips were dipped in these solutions for exactly 60 s in each case.

Emeraldine base (0.5 g) was stirred with 40.00 ml of TMU, centrifuged, the centrifugate was filtered through a filter paper. The extractability was about 40% in TMU.

1.00 ml of this saturated solution was placed on the steel strip in two installments.

The next installment was added before the first one became dry in the oven at 100°. The strip was taken out as soon as it dried. It was used for corrosion monitoring.

Addition of a corrosion inhibitor :

10 drops of *N*-allylaniline were added to 10.0 ml of emeraldine base solution. After pretreatment 1.0 ml of this solution was placed on the steel and dried in the oven at 100°.

Addition of titanium tetrachloride :

A 1×10^{-6} solution of titanium tetrachloride was prepared in cyclohexane and 0.10 ml of this solution was added to 10.0 ml of emeraldine base. 1.0 ml of this solution was placed on the steel strip and dried in the oven.

Treatment with $TiCl_4$:

The steel strip was dipped in 1×10^{-6} M $TiCl_4$ for 10 min, pretreated and then 1.0 ml of emeraldine base was placed on it and dried in the oven.

Treatment with Premium Plastic Wrap (PPW) :

The steel strip was pretreated with one of the two pretreating solutions. 0.1 g of PPW was added to 10.0 ml of emeraldine base solution in TMU. 1.0 ml of this solution was placed on the steel and dried in the oven.

Use of allyl aniline as a corrosion inhibitor and PPW :

The steel strip is pretreated with one of the two pretreatment solutions. 10.0 ml emeraldine solution was mixed with 0.1 g PPW and 10 drops of *N*-allylaniline. 1.00 ml of this solution was placed on the steel strip and allowed to dry in the oven.

The steel strip is pretreated with one of the two pretreatment solutions. 1.0 ml emeraldine solution was placed on the steel strip and 0.01 g PPW and a drop of *N*-allylaniline was added and the solution on the steel strip was allowed to evaporate.

Corrosion monitoring was done in 0.1 M HCl solution.

References

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